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Patient derived xenografts in HPV+ and HPV- cancer.

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Citations

1. Larmour, L.I., Cousins, F.L., Teague, J.A., Deane, J.A., Jobling, T.W. and Gargett, C.E., 2018. A patient derived xenograft model of cervical cancer and cervical dysplasia. PLoS One, 13(10), p.e0206539.
2. Scott, C.L., Mackay, H.J. and Haluska Jr, P., 2014. Patient-derived xenograft models in gynecologic malignancies. American Society of Clinical Oncology Educational Book, 34(1), pp.e258-e266.

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